

INFLUENCE OF HOME AND SCHOOL ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS ON CUMULATIVE CHILDREN LEARNING IN PRIMARY SCHOOLS

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Abstract:

Several studies examined the relationship which exists among home, school, learners and teacher-related factors and academic performance in different subjects at various levels of education. Intriguingly, there seems to be meager literature and diverse opinions on how majority of these factors affect children cumulative learning in classroom instructional process at the primary school level. This study therefore examined the influence of home and school environmental factors on cumulative children learning in primary schools. Descriptive survey research design was adopted. Four research hypotheses guided the study. A sample size of 150 pupils eventually participated from five (5) schools in Ijebu-Ode Local Government Area of Ogun State. The Home and School-Related Factors Scale (HS-RFS) and Primary Schools Cumulative Results (PSCRs) were used to gather data for the study while Pearson Product Moment Correlation and Multiple Regression statistical tools were used for data analysis. The results showed that there is significant correlation between home and school environmental factors and children cumulative learning in primary schools (Home Environment: $B = .236$ (23.6%), $P < 0.05$; School Facilities: $B = .205$ (20.5%), $P < 0.05$; School Location: $B = .135$ (13.5%), $P < 0.05$). In view of the findings, it is recommended that communities, school administrators and government representatives still need to work collaboratively to improve on those factors which contribute to pupils' learning in order to enhance the output from curriculum instructional process in primary schools.

Keywords: home environment, learning, school facilities, school location

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1. Introduction

The acquisition of knowledge, skills and habit formation that are worthwhile are often transmitted to a person, but in this context, children through formal and informal education which takes place not only in schools but also within families, communities and the society at large. The communities and societies are expected to work collaboratively with educational institutions for effective upbringing, socializing and educating the children. As a result, schools cannot and should not operate as separate entities within the society since each group plays different roles in contributing to children's education (Lawal, Oduwaiye & Murtala, 2015). The school performs its function in children education through the curriculum, and it is the subject matter of the curriculum which serves as part of the educational values to prepare children to contribute to the betterment of the society through the cumulative learning which results at the end of their education.

Learning, this is a process that depends on experience and leads to long-term changes in behavioural patterns, takes place most effectively when different factors and groups collaborate. That is why educators continue to advocate for partnership development among schools, parents and communities for enhanced learning in schools. Learning implies changes related directed to experience (Hergenbahn, 2005). Many research studies have identified various ways and factors which culminate into learning at all levels of education and in different subjects and specialization. For instance, Pmirin (2013) cited Greenbush (1999) who found out that a child's learning attainment are traceable to home factors. Also, researches in recent years have indicated the importance of environment in effective teaching-learning process for curriculum success. Some of the factors responsible for academic performance include finance, parental, environmental, health factors, and the likes. Individual, environmental and health factors are responsible for good academic performance of any student (Olusola, 2008).

Home is where the child, the parent or guardians live and from where the child set out to and fro to school. Home is the first environmental contact of the child where he or she is firstly prepared for school work. This is because parents and guardians and other family members in the home are children first set of teachers. From the day, a child is born and begins to hear, he or she begins to develop literacy as parents and other caring adults and pre-school teachers speak, play, sing and read to them. As a child moves from infant to toddler and then to preschooler, he learns to be able to read, listen and speak (Yan & Lin, 2012). The child often sees the parents, siblings and things in their immediate environment to be most significant, and they are capable of promoting or diminishing him in self-worth and learning (Ekanem, 2004). It becomes clear that educational success of children's learning abilities depends on home environment.

In addition, when the child reaches school age and enters school, he still has a substantial fraction of his time at home with his family. Thus, home environment, whether physical or psychological has much to do with children education. Physical

environment deals with material aspects such as infrastructure, availability of facilities, home economy, cultural background, location, etc. some of those factors are home factors while some others can be school factors or both. The psychological environment includes the emotions and other attitudinal factors around the child. The quality of home is very important in child's education. Some have a history or tradition of formal education and modern influences, while some are not so well equipped with formal education and modern facilities and quality home background.

Studies have shown that if a child lives in an impoverished environment for the first four years of life, he is likely to lose as many as, in reading, knowledge and skill. It is the environment which provides the necessary conditions for both physical and intellectual growth. A child who is handicapped by ill-health, lack of motivation, nutritional deficiencies, and unfair criticisms is prone of being affected intellectually considering the negative impact such factors will have on his self-concept to learn both at home and in school.

On school environment, school location, school facilities, teachers' personalities, method of teaching and the classroom are among the factors which influence teaching-learning process. Operationally, physical facilities could be said to be objects/structures which promote the course of action or operation in the teaching-learning process. Obiedumani & Obielumani (2015) have reported a strong correlation between educational facilities and students' academic performance. Such educational physical facilities like classroom or buildings (lecture halls/classrooms and theatres), laboratories, equipment, libraries, workshops, administrative and staff offices, utilities are required both in quantity and quality to house and midwife the various school subjects and courses at all educational levels in curriculum instructional process. As a result, numerous factors ranging from home factor, school factor, learners' factor, parental factor and many others influence children learning.

On school location, Adepoju and Akinwumi (2001) reported the most of the secondary schools in Oyo, Ondo, Lagos and Kwara State are arbitrarily located and distributed. This has resulted in the poor performance of students and high cost of secondary education. They buttressed that some schools are located very far from the students' homes, while others are sited in small land areas which lack space for expansion. Some schools are even built near highways or near markets or industrial centres. In another available literature, it was found out that many schools are concentrated in urban areas at the expense of rural areas. Thus, geographical location of school becomes another factor of note in children's learning.

From the available literature reviewed and from the obvious observations of the researchers, the effect or impact of most of the factors enumerated above have been given considerations in respect of specific subjects available in Nigerian primary, secondary and tertiary levels. However, their influence on cumulative children learning has not be vividly given due attention. Meanwhile, it is the cumulative learners' results that are often used for promotion to the next academic class in most cases if not all. It is worth mentioning that cumulative results are a combination of formative evaluation of learners added together overtime in a systematic manner within the school academic

year. No doubt, the system of one-shot examination to determine children's learning had long been frowned at overtime. In fact, due to inherent weakness in the one-shot system of examination, continuous assessment was introduced (Essuman & Portuphy, 2012).

More importantly, cumulative learning is determined by a systematic consideration and addition of continuous assessment and terminal results for a whole year, in this context, at the primary school level in all the subjects in the process of educating the child. Numerous factors are therefore involved in such cumulative learning of learners. This, according to some concerned individuals and stakeholders, the writers of this paper inclusive, often results relatively in the low or higher performances of learners, and more importantly relative learning. As a result, this study was embarked upon.

2. Statement of the Problem

Till date, learning outcomes of children in Nigeria primary schools during curriculum implementation have attracted many criticisms. It has however observed that numerous factors affect children learning in primary schools. Although, several studies have examined the relationship which exists among home, school, learners and teacher-related factors and academic performance in different subjects at various levels of education, intriguingly, there seems to be meager literature and diverse opinions on how majority of these factors affect children cumulative learning in classroom instructional process at the primary school level.

Such factors as family income, school location, means of transportation to school, number of family siblings, parental educational level, matrimonial condition, home training, parental support, school atmosphere, classroom condition, spacing, library services, availability and functionality of school facilities and equipment, laboratories and school clinic among others become important factors to reckon with in children learning. It is on the above observations and the literature reviewed which prompted this study to examine the influence of home and school environmental factors on cumulative children learning in primary schools.

2.1 Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study is to examine the influence of home and school environmental factors on cumulative children learning in primary schools. The specific purposes of this study are to;

1. examine the influence of home environment on cumulative children learning in primary schools.
2. examine the influence of school location on cumulative children learning in primary schools
3. examine the influence of school facilities on cumulative children learning in primary schools

4. examine the joint influence of home environment, school location and school facilities on cumulative children learning in primary schools

2.2 Research Hypotheses

Ho1: There is no significant correlation between home environment and cumulative children learning in primary schools

Ho2: There is no significant correlation between school location and cumulative children learning in primary schools

Ho3: There is no significant correlation between school facilities and cumulative children learning in primary schools

Ho4: There is no significant combined effect of home environment, school location and school facilities on cumulative children learning in primary schools.

2.3 Scope of the Study

This study focuses on the influence of home and school environmental factors on cumulative children learning in primary schools in Ijebu-Ode Local Government Area of Ogun State. It is limited to primary five pupils (male and female) in public primary schools in the study area for 2015/2016 academic session.

3. Research Methodology

The description of research methodology which guided the study as a plan of the action is presented as follows.

3.1 Research Design

The descriptive survey research design was adopted for this study because it is a non-experimental study, and the variables have occurred much earlier in the population and so they were only measured and not manipulated in the study

3.2 Population of the Study

The target population for this study comprised all pupils in public primary schools in Ijebu-Ode Local Government Area of Ogun State.

3.3 Sample and Sampling Technique

Five (5) public primary schools were purposively selected from the twenty (20) public primary schools in Ijebu-Ode Local Government based on their location conditioned by the major communities/environment and obvious serene of the school environmental climate by observation. The total population of the pupils in the selected five (5) schools is 562. A sample size of 168 respondents were purposively selected from the primary schools based on their attendance, regularly and participation in the three (3) terms examinations for 2015/2016 academic session in all the primary school subjects without any absent in any of their subjects. In all, one hundred and sixty-eight (168) pupils (male and female) were selected for the study.

3.4 Research Instrument

The research instruments used for data collection are: (I) Home and School-Related Factors Scale (HS-RFS) (II) Primary School Cumulative Results (PSCRs). The HS-RFS was divided into two sections: A, B and C. section A contained items which sought information from the selected respondents about their demographic data such as gender, age, class, school location, etc. while Section B contained eight (8) prominent indicators of children home environment and Section C contained ten (10) items on indicators of school environmental factor. In all, section B & C contained eighteen items. The Primary Schools Cumulative Results (PSCRs) used for 2015/2016 pupil' s scores were collected as standardized cumulative learning scores for each school. altogether, PSCRs contained 168 pupils' cumulative scores for 2015/2016 academic session.

3.5 Validity of Research Instruments

The research instrument (Home and School-Related Factors Scale – HS-RFS) was given out to some experts in instrument design and evaluation for vetting in term of item phrasing, coverage, relevance and adequacy while the Primary Schools Cumulative Results (PSCRs) was considered valid based on the head of each school' s stamp and signature to ascertain that the cumulative scores given by primary five class teachers were indeed authentic.

3.6 Reliability of the Research Instrument

Twenty-five copies of Home and School-Related Factors Scale (HS-RFS) was administered to primary five pupils in some other schools outside the scope of the study once and Cronbach Alpha reliability co-efficient of 0.72 obtained was considered reliable for the study.

3.7 Method of Data Collection

The five schools covered in the study were visited immediately after their third term examination by the researchers and some of the class teachers in the schools assisted for data collection on HS-RFS and Primary Schools Cumulative Results based on the head teachers approval. The data collection lasted for 3 days but it was discovered that 18 pupils did not return their own instrument at the time of collecting it back because they were absent. In all, 150 returned HS-RFS were eventually used for data analysis in this study.

3.8 Method of Data Analysis

The data collected through the research instrument were analysed using the mean, standard deviation, Pearson Moment Correlation and Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA) to test the formulated research hypotheses upon which the results and interpretation were done. The correlation was determined by the r value, while the level of significance was determined by $P < 0.05$ to be considered significant, but not significant if $P > 0.05$ in this study (for research Hypotheses 1, 2 & 3). For research hypotheses 4, the collective and relative influence of home factor, school location and

school facilities were interpreted using the regression analysis as also presented in the results of the study.

4. Results

The results of the study are presented as follows as guided by the research hypotheses raised for the study.

4.1 Testing of Research Hypotheses

Ho1: There is no significant correlation between home environment and cumulative children learning in primary schools.

Table 1: Correlation Analysis between Home Environment and Cumulative Children Learning

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	r	P	Remark
Home Environment	1.19	386	150	.219**	.007	Sig.
Cumulative Children Learning	1.20	401				

**Correlation is significant at 0.05 alpha level

Table 1 shows that there is significant correlation between home environment and cumulative children learning in primary schools ($r = .219xx$, $N = 150$, $P < 0.05$). The null hypothesis 1 is therefore rejected while the alternate hypothesis is accepted. This implies that the pupils' home environment influence their cumulative learning significantly.

Ho2: There is no significant correlation between school location and cumulative children learning in primary schools.

Table 2: Correlation Analysis between School Location and Cumulative Children Learning

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	r	P	Remark
School Location	2.34	1.340	150	-.502**	.000	Sig
Cumulative Children Learning	1.20	.401				

**Correlation is significant at 0.05 alpha level

Table 2 shows that there is significant correlation between school location and cumulative learning in primary schools ($r = -.502xx$, $N = 150$, $P < 0.05$). The null hypothesis is therefore rejected while the alternate hypothesis is accepted. This implies that school location has significant influence on children cumulative learning in primary schools.

Ho3: There is no significant correlation between school facilities and cumulative children learning in primary schools

Table 3: Correlation Analysis between School Facilities and Cumulative Children Learning

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	r	P	Remark
School Location	1.73	.447	150	.307**	.000	Sig
Cumulative Children Learning	1.20	.401				

The result in table 3 indicate that there is significant relationship between school facilities and cumulative children learning in primary schools ($r = .307$, $N = 150$, $P < 0.05$). The null hypothesis (H_03) is therefore rejected while the alternate hypothesis is accepted. This implies that school facilities such as classroom condition, computer laboratory, library services, spacing, store room, toilet and toilet facilities, chairs and lockers, tables, shelves, etc. have significant influence on children cumulative learning in primary schools.

H₀₄: There is no significant combined effect of home environment, school location and school facilities on cumulative children learning in primary schools.

Table 4a: Regression Analysis of Home Environment, School Location, School Facilities and Cumulative Children Learning

Model	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Significance	Remark
Regression	8.328	3	2.776	25.862	0.000b	Sig.
Residual	15.672	146	.107			
Total	24.000	149				

(a) Dependent Variable Cumulative Children learning

(b) Predictors (Constant): Home Environment (B1), School Location (b2) and School Facilities (b3)

Collectively from table 4a, there is significant influence of home environment, school location and school facilities on children learning which implies that home environment (b1), School location (b2) and School facilities (b3) are strong enough to predict cumulative children learning. This is shown by the value of .000b which is less than the significant alpha level of .05. the collective influence of home environment, school location and school facilities on cumulative children learning in primary schools is 10.7% and this is significant at $P = .000b < 0.05$ level of significance.

Table 4b: Relative Influence of Home Environment, School Location and School Facilities on Cumulative Children Learning

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients				Standard T	
	B	Rank	Std. Dev.	Coeff. Beta		
(Constant)	.880		.157	.	5.589	.000
Home Environment	.236	1 st	.068	.233	3.461	.001
School Location	-.135	3 rd	.021	-.450	-6.574	.000
School Facilities	.205	2 nd	.062	.229	3.331	.001

a. Dependent Variable Cumulative Children Learning

Table 4b presents the analysis of the influence of home environment, school location and school facilities on children learning. Relatively, the table shows that there is significant influence of home environment on cumulative children learning ($.000 < P = .05$). Also, there is significant influence of school location on cumulative children learning ($.000 < P = .05$), and school location also significantly influence cumulative children learning in the study ($.001 < P = .05$). The order of significant influence of the three factors is: Home environment -.234 (23.6%); School facilities -.205 (20.5%); and School location -.135 (13.5%) respectively as shown by the β value in each case in table 4b.

5. Discussion of Findings

The results of the study revealed that there is significant influence between home environment and cumulative children learning in primary schools. This study partly negates the findings of Izundu (2005) who found out that most pupils in primary schools in Anambra State come from low socio-economic families but it does not affect their learning adversely. However, his study found that there is significant relationship between the level of parents' education and the effective learning of the pupils which is part of home environment indicators built into the research instrument of this study.

The findings of Onyi (2002) on the influence of home on the effective learning of pupils in Enugu East Local Government Area of Enugu State are corroborated by the finding of this study. That parental residence influences the effective learning of the pupils. Also, that there is positive correlation between parents encouragement and pupils effective learning. Onyi's study is related to the present study in that it is geared towards exploring how home environmental factors influence pupils effective learning. Eke (2009) who conducted a study on the relationship between home environmental factors and effective learning of primary school pupils in Gboko Local Government Area of Benue State discovered that parental occupation does not significantly affect effective learning of pupils and likewise parental educational background is not significantly related to effective learning of primary school pupils. These findings imply that geographical locations and influences of home factors on learners' learning vary from place to place, region to region, still, they contribute to pupils' cumulative learning, though may not be significant in all cases.

On school location which significantly influence cumulative children learning in this study agree with the report of Adepaju and Akinwumi (2001) who cited some available literature that students' academic performance was significantly related to geographical location of schools, aesthetic values such as trees, shrubs and flower beds which beautify schools and create good learning atmosphere. Similarly, school physical facilities which influence children cumulative learning in this study consolidates the observations of Oredein (2010) that the prevailing condition of infrastructure as well as instructional materials in public primary schools in Nigeria which are poor would definitely show a negative influence on the instructional quality in public schools which may translate to poor learning, poor attitude and poor values for primary school pupils.

On a general note, the findings of this study have made it clear that the environment (home and school among others) plays a major role in children education in curriculum implementation process and in parental contributions on children from home. Environmental factors help in the development and pattern of academic skill, and that children are encouraged through interaction with teachers, classmates and their classroom materials (Gessel, 2011) cited in Omirin, 2013). Home-related factors and school-related factors in sum constitute important variables in classroom instruction and in teaching profession generally. They are indispensable to a good learning environment. Adequate consideration given to them determines in no small measure the cumulative learning that would take place in the life of school-going children.

6. Conclusion

This study which examined the influence of home and school environmental factors on cumulative children learning in primary schools has indeed revealed that the factors considered hold significant position if at all effective curriculum delivery is to take place. The home has its own role to play vis-à-vis the schools which altogether anchor many indicators which influence learning.

In institution of learning, they are of crucial importance to the teaching and learning process. Where the home and the school environment are conducive, one complements the other and learning is promoted. Irrespective of the geographical location of schools and home background of learners, this paper concludes that greater attention still needs to be given to myriad of factors which relatively and jointly influence positively or mar learning in that there negative influence could be continuously reduced to the barest minimum for effective learning.

6.1 Recommendations

The following recommendations are made for immediate and future education planning and all to enhance the output from curriculum instructional process in educational institutions. They are:

1. Communities, school administrators and government representatives still need to work more collaboratively to improve on those factors which contribute to pupils learning from their respective responsibilities towards these future leaders.
2. Adequate maintenance culture is recommended for school administrators and their other staff for adequate care of available school facilities/resources, and build effective school climate and culture
3. Parents, guardians and caregivers need re-orientation and proper enlightenment on children home care so that priority would also be given to children education among other commitments or burden which may surround them in their daily lives.

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